

ANALYSIS OF THE SIGNIFICANCE AND CONCEPTS OF PERSONNEL POLICY IN INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES

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Annotation: This article sheds light on the importance of the personnel policy carried out in the internal affairs bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as some concepts related to this topic are analyzed and author's definitions for them are developed.

Basic (most important) words: personnel, personnel policy, personnel selection, personnel training.

To what extent all the priorities of state policy in economic, social and in other spheres are carried out directly depends on the personnel carrying out these tasks. Therefore, qualified personnel are a guarantee of the prosperity and bright future of the country.

President of The Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. M. Mirziyoyev on the issue of training personnel at the event on the occasion of the day of teachers and coaches, said: "Today the society in which we live needs a new opinion, a new idea, and most importantly, a new generation of personnel capable of carrying out reforms. If every day they ask what torments me, without hesitation I will answer that the personnel torments, the personnel reserve torments. It is no coincidence that we have spent 25 years avidly honoring the staff and not caring for them respectfully, so now we do not have the staff" [1].

If we dwell on the importance of personnel policy in public administration, this is a very important issue, of course. Because, the proper implementation of human resources policy in any state serves to ensure that all areas are operated in a stable way, as well as to guarantee that these areas will develop in stages [2].

While the issue of analyzing the main concepts related to the topic will be touched upon, first of all, it is important to find an answer to the question of what is personnel policy. To this concept, politicians, sociologists and legal scholars have tried to express their opinions through their different views. In Particular, V.A. Nefedov: "Personnel policy is a strategy for the formation and rational use of the personnel potential of the state [3]", by this he tried to express this concept briefly and clearly.

I.A. Shentyabina, on the other hand, comments: "The meaning and purpose of personnel policy is to provide conditions for the maximum determination of personnel potential, including in order to achieve the goals of the management entity, since any personnel policy can be effective when the goals of the subject are in accordance with the goals of its object [4]".

J.Q. Yusubov cites the definition: "Personnel policy is a strategy for managing the process of professional potential and its rational use, working with personnel is determining the main directions and priorities in personal management [5]".

V.A. Yaskov: "Personnel policy, first of all, is defining strategic and tactical lines, determining the scientific principles of personnel selection, placement and training,

determining the goals and objectives of working with personnel, forms and methods, directions, character, requirements for personnel in the specific historical conditions of a particular period of the country [6]", -by stating this opinion he gave a wider coverage of this concept

V.R. Vesnin, on the other hand, said: "personnel policy is a system of theoretical views, ideas, requirements, principles that determine the main directions of working with personnel, its forms and methods [7]", -tried to reveal in general the content and essence of personnel policy.

A.Ya. Kibanov also said: "Personnel policy is a system of knowledge, views, principles, methods and practical measures of government bodies and organizations at the basic level of management, aimed at determining the goals, tasks, forms and methods of working with personnel in all areas of human activity [8]", giving a general definition.

By M.Dosimbek to this concept: "Personnel policy is an integral part of the general policy for the implementation of personnel activities aimed at providing personnel through the selection, reception, placement, training and use of personnel in accordance with the current legislation to increase the labor potential of a state body, organizations and social groups [9]", - an attempt has been made to give a more

T.S. Jumanov "Personnel policy is one of the most essential areas of state policy and is the activity of the state in the selection, reception, training, their placement and staffing of personnel,"- clearly and succinctly described.

In general, from the above definitions, personnel policy is considered as one of the most important issues at the level of public policy, the role of the country tomorrow in development, world cooperation will depend precisely on qualified personnel. Therefore, the issue of objectively, openly and transparently selecting personnel, training them at a professional level, placing them in place and ensuring the stability of personnel is the main criterion of personnel policy.

When talking about personnel policy, of course, it is advisable to highlight the content of such concepts as the frame, which is considered an integral part of this concept, their preparation, selection, placement, personnel potential, personnel reserve [10].

A cadre refers to a specialist, employee who is active in one field or another. Some employees work in production, other employees in service or as a civil servant in the relevant state and local authorities. It is not only about a specialist with higher education, but also about specialists with secondary, secondary special education as they can also be included in the ranks of an employee (cadre) (gardener, locksmith, etc.). In addition, a person can also work in state organizations, having the appropriate specialty, studying in training courses in any field, for example, as a programmer with a background in Information Technology, and etc.

The Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek language gives this concept: "cadre (cadres-personnel composition) - the service, worker and staff of the enterprise, institution with special training [11]", and emphasized the issue of having exactly the training.

In the National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, similar to the above definition, i.e.: "personnel (France. cadre-personnel content) - 1) the main composition of qualified employees in enterprises, institutions, firms, joint-stock companies, banks, trade unions and public organizations [12]", and it is also emphasized that the feature of "competence" distinguishes this concept from other concepts.

Another source in the legal encyclopedia also refers to this concept in the content of the above expressed and commented that: "personnel (France. cadre-personnel composition) – the main (state-specific) composition of the employees of the organization, all permanent employees [13]".

J.G.R. Yusubov, on the other hand, said: "usually, "cadre" is understood to mean persons in a certain direction, with a specific specialty, knowledge and experience, at the same time working in a particular team [14]", giving a more specific definition than those presented above.

The concept of "Personnel" itself is also comprehensive, and the concepts of "specialist personnel", "executive personnel", "management personnel " have different aspects. "Specialist personnel" refers more specifically to personnel with a specialty in one direction, with bachelor's and master's degrees, working in a particular field of science and production, that is, state power and management. It is from the specialist personnel base that the reserve of managerial personnel is formed [15].

"Personnel selection", on the other hand, is understood only as the process of sorting mainly more responsible workers-employees into one or another position among the personnel operating in the relevant field [16]. Therefore, there is also a large difference between the concepts of "selection of personnel" and "selection of candidates(applicants)for work or study".

In our opinion, the selection of candidates is mainly understood as the process of sorting out from multitude of candidates to work in any field or study in educational institutions of any specialty, depending on the production or specialty.

A candidate who has been sorted (selectively) to study at a production or educational institution will officially have the status of an employee or student.

The selected candidate is prepared in accordance with state requirements, state educational standards, curriculum and science programs for becoming the future mature specialist in the relevant field, if there is a student. A graduate student is sent to production (practice) so that he can put into practice the theoretical knowledge he has acquired in an educational institution. Employers appoint a suitable position for the graduate, depending on his specialty.

Usually, a competition is announced for existing free (vacant) positions, the conditions and requirements of the competition are determined based on the specifics of that office. For example, qualification requirements for the position of a vacancy can also be: education, specialty, work experience, foreign language proficiency, computer literacy and other additional requirements [17].

On May 5, 2014, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the openness of the activities of state authorities and management bodies" and the Presidential Decree No. PD 6247 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 16, 2021 "On additional measures to ensure the openness of the activities of state bodies and organizations, as well as effective implementation of public control" [18] made it possible for individuals and legal entities to be aware of and use information about the activities of state authorities and management bodies.

In our republic, in 2020, the only open portal of State Civil Service vacancies was launched under the slogan "open road to public service". The open portal openly provides information about the supreme bodies of state government, committees and centers, state inspectorates, special state government bodies, committees, ministries, agencies, central institutions, vacant

positions in state unitary enterprises [19]. At the same time, through this portal, it is possible to monitor the number of organizations, participants in contests, resumes, test participants, participants in a conversation, number of recruits, comparative statistical indicators in the cross-sectional years in an online mode.

The process of training personnel is carried out mainly by the composition of professors and teachers in higher educational institutions.

A graduate of an educational institution in a certain area of expertise acquires the appropriate skill by applying the knowledge gained in practice, and over the years this skill gradually becomes a qualification due to gaining experience. The qualifications of personnel are also systematically increased from time to time by the relevant educational institutions, depending on the nature of the specialty.

In production, personnel can also be retrained, which means, retraining the employee in the direction of another specialty in one area, depending on the need and requirements.

Training of qualified personnel is carried out mainly in higher education institutions. Higher education institutions prepare future personnel in accordance with state educational standards, state requirements, curriculum and science programs and world educational standards in a field of study.

Personnel trained in higher education institutions are assigned to the corresponding positions in state or non-governmental organizations by competent officials in the relevant areas of mutualism. Of course, it is advisable that this appointment corresponds to the specialty of the employee (cadres), otherwise the need may arise for them to retrain the personnel. After the appointment of an employee (cadre) to the appropriate position, work activity begins and during his career, skill dressing is carried out, putting into practice the theoretical knowledge gained in higher education institutions with the support of coaches, and this skill becomes a qualification step by step, resulting in a qualified cadre. It is also possible for an employee during his work career to be recommended for higher positions, depending on the coefficient of performance, or to serve in a position at an unattainable level. This criterion is important when placing personnel in place.

The order of service of personnel (employees) in the relevant organizations is regulated by the relevant regulatory legal acts. For example, the order of service of civil servants of the state is regulated by the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on civil service of the state" dated on August 8, 2022 [20].

Based on the above conclusions, we consider it appropriate to develop authorship definitions for the following concepts:

Selection of personnel is the process of selection and appointment of a certain requirement and conditions (concourses) to a particular position (other equal or higher) from among the specialists operating in the production itself and with the appropriate qualifications.

Selection of candidates is the process of sorting out the most optimal among candidates under the appropriate requirements and conditions for their future activity in production, and the most knowledgeable among candidates for study in educational institutions.

Training of personnel is the process of training students in educational institutions for future work activities in accordance with state requirements, state educational standards, curriculum and science programs in the direction of the relevant specialty.

Placing personnel in place-placing (appointment) of employees (personnel) in a position that is suitable and worthy for them, depending on the appropriate specialty, results of work activities, qualifications.

Personnel policy in law enforcement agencies of our country is carried out at the level of public policy in a systematic and purposeful way.

The internal affairs bodies occupy an important place among law enforcement agencies in ensuring peace and tranquility in our country. In the implementation of tasks in the main areas of activity of internal affairs bodies, it is important to correctly select personnel in the system, train professional personnel and put them in place, and correctly organize service activities.

As a result of the above analyzes, and taking into account the general definitions given to the selection of candidates, personnel selection, their preparation, based on the nature of the activities of the internal affairs bodies, author's definitions of the following concepts were developed:

Selection of personnel in the internal affairs bodies is the process of sorting (selection) of candidates with qualifications in the relevant specialty operating in the internal affairs bodies for a particular position (other equivalent or higher) on the basis of appropriate requirements and conditions (competitions).

Selection of candidates for the internal affairs bodies is the process of sorting (selecting) them according to the appropriate requirements and conditions from multitude of candidates who have expressed a desire to serve in the internal affairs bodies or study in educational institutions in the future.

Training of personnel in internal affairs bodies – the process of training cadets and listeners in educational institutions of internal affairs bodies in accordance with state requirements, state educational standards, curriculum and science programs in the direction of the relevant specialty is understood.

Placement of personnel in the internal affairs bodies-the placement (appointment) of employees of the internal affairs bodies (personnel) on the basis of the relevant criteria, depending on the direction, specialty, results of work activities, qualifications, in the position corresponding to them.

In conclusion, personnel policy is considered as one of the priorities of the state, the correct implementation of personnel policy in our country serves to strengthen the development of any sphere and the guarantee of reliable protection of the rights and legitimate interests of citizens.

